
NEWTON SEQUENCES AND DIRICHLET CONVOLUTION

Klaudiusz Wójcik

Faculty of Mathematics, Jagiellonian University, Kraków, Poland
 Klaudiusz.Wojcik@uj.edu.pl

Received: 12/4/20, Revised: 4/20/21, Accepted: 5/29/21, Published: 6/3/21

Abstract

An integer sequence $a : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ is called a *Newton sequence* generated by the sequence of integers $c : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$, if the following *Newton identities* hold

$$a(n) = c(1)a(n-1) + \dots + c(n-1)a(1) + nc(n).$$

We show that a is a Newton sequence if and only if

$$\sum_{d|n} f(d)a(n/d) \equiv 0 \pmod{n}, \quad n \geq 1,$$

for every function $f : \mathbb{N} \rightarrow \mathbb{Z}$ satisfying the two conditions

$$\sum_{d|n} f(d) \equiv 0 \pmod{n}, \quad f(1) = \pm 1.$$

In particular, f may be the Möbius function, the Euler totient function or the Jordan totient function.

1. Introduction

We recall some basic facts concerning Dirichlet involution (see [2]). Let $\mathcal{A}(\mathbb{C})$ be the set of all complex-valued arithmetical functions, i.e., the set of functions defined on \mathbb{N} with values in \mathbb{C} . By $\mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z}) \subset \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{C})$ we denote the set of all integer-valued sequences. The *Dirichlet convolution* of functions $f, g \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{C})$ is the function $f * g \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{C})$ defined by

$$(f * g)(n) = \sum_{d|n} f(d)g(n/d) = \sum_{d_1 d_2 = n} f(d_1)g(d_2), \quad n \geq 1.$$

For any non-empty subsets A, B of $\mathcal{A}(\mathbb{C})$ we put

$$A * B := \{a * b : a \in A, b \in B\}.$$

We distinguish the following integer-valued sequences:

(ϵ) the *multiplicative identity with respect to Dirichlet convolution*:

$$\epsilon(n) = \left[\frac{1}{n} \right] = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } n = 1 \\ 0, & \text{if } n > 1, \end{cases}$$

(μ) the *Möbius function* μ :

$$\mu(n) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } n = 1 \\ (-1)^r, & \text{if } n \text{ is a product of } r \text{ different primes} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

(I_k) $I_k(n) = n^k$ for $k \geq 0$,

(S_f) the *divisor sum* over $f \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$:

$$S_f(n) := f * I_0(n) = \sum_{d|n} f(d), \quad n \geq 1,$$

(φ) the *Euler totient function* φ :

$$\varphi(n) = \mu * I_1(n) = \sum_{\substack{1 \leq k \leq n \\ (k,n)=1}} 1,$$

(J_k) the *Jordan totient function* J_k :

$$J_k(n) = \mu * I_k(n) = \sum_{\substack{1 \leq a_1, \dots, a_k \leq n \\ (a_1, \dots, a_k, n)=1}} 1.$$

The set of arithmetical functions $\mathcal{A}(\mathbb{C})$ is a commutative ring under pointwise addition and Dirichlet convolution. The invertible elements of this ring are the arithmetical functions f with $f(1) \neq 0$. The following well-known facts will be useful later ([2]):

- (1) $S_\mu = \mu * I_0 = \epsilon$,
- (2) the *Möbius inversion formula*: $S_f = f * I_0$ if and only if $f = \mu * S_f$,
- (3) $S_\varphi = I_1$,
- (4) $S_{J_k} = I_k$.

Definition 1. Let $a \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$ be a sequence of integers. We say that $a \equiv 0$, if

$$a(n) \equiv 0 \pmod{n},$$

for all $n \geq 1$.

We put

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{A}^*(\mathbb{Z}) &:= \{a \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z}) : a(1) = \pm 1\}, \\ \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z}) &:= \{a \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z}) : a \equiv 0\}, \\ \mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z}) &:= \mathcal{A}^*(\mathbb{Z}) \cap \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z}), \\ \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{Z}) &:= \{f \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z}) : S_f \in \mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z})\}. \end{aligned}$$

Example 2. It follows that $I_k \in \mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z})$ and $\mu, \varphi, J_k \in \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{Z})$.

Corollary 3.

- (1) Every $a \in \mathcal{A}^*(\mathbb{Z})$ admits an inverse $a^{-1} \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$,
- (2) $\mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z}) * \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z}) \subset \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$,
- (3) $\mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z}) * \mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z}) \subset \mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z})$,
- (4) $(\mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z}), *)$ is the commutative group,
- (5) $\mathcal{M}(\mathbb{Z}) = \{\mu * g : g \in \mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z})\}$.

Proof. The conditions (1) and (5) are obvious. If $a, b \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$, then

$$a * b(n) = \sum_{d|n} a(d)b(n/d) \equiv 0 \pmod{n},$$

hence (2) follows. We claim that $a^{-1} \equiv 0$ for $a \in \mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z})$. We use the induction on n . It is trivial for $n = 1$. For $n > 1$, by [[2], Theorem 2.8] and the inductive step, we get that

$$a^{-1}(n) = \pm \sum_{\substack{d|n \\ d>1}} a(d)a^{-1}(n/d) \equiv 0 \pmod{n}.$$

□

Definition 4 (Newton sequence). A sequence of integers $a \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$ is called a *Newton sequence* generated by the sequence of integers $c \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$, if the following *Newton identities* hold: for all $n \in \mathbb{N}$

$$a(n) = c(1)a(n-1) + \dots + c(n-1)a(1) + nc(n).$$

Denote by $\mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$ the set of Newton sequences, i.e.,

$$\mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z}) = \{a : a \text{ is a Newton sequence generated by a sequence of integers } c\}.$$

Example 5 (Sequence of traces). For a square integer matrix $A \in M_l(\mathbb{Z})$ we define a *sequence of traces* $\text{tr}[A] \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$ by

$$(\text{tr}[A])_n := \text{tr } A^n, \quad n \geq 1.$$

It follows by the classical Newton’s identities that a Newton sequence $a \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$ is generated by a finite sequence $c = (c(1), \dots, c(l)) \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$ (i.e., $c(n) = 0$ for $n > l$) if and only if a is the sequence of traces $\text{tr}[A]$, where A is the *companion matrix* of the monic polynomial $w(x) = x^l - c(1)x^{l-1} - \dots - c(l-1)x - c(l) \in \mathbb{Z}[x]$, i.e.,

$$A := A[c(1), \dots, c(l)] := \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & c(l) \\ 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & c(l-1) \\ 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 & c(l-2) \\ \vdots & 0 & \ddots & 0 & \vdots \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & 1 & c(1) \end{bmatrix} \in M_l(\mathbb{Z}).$$

Since $w(X) = \det(XI_l - A) \in \mathbb{Z}[X]$, the eigenvalues of A are the roots of w .

Definition 6 (Dold-Fermat sequence [6]). A sequence $a \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$ is called a *Dold-Fermat sequence*, if $\mu * a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$, i.e.,

$$\sum_{d|n} \mu(d) a(n/d) \equiv 0 \pmod{n}, \quad n \geq 1.$$

In combinatorics and number theory, Dold-Fermat sequences have also been called *pre-realizable sequences*, *relatively realizable sequences*, *Gauss sequences* and *generalized Fermat sequences* ([1, 3, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13, 14]).

We prove the following theorem.

Theorem 7. For $a \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$ the following conditions are equivalent:

- (1) a is a Newton sequence,
- (2) a is a Dold-Fermat sequence,
- (3) $f * a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$, i.e.,

$$\sum_{d|n} f(d) a(n/d) \equiv 0 \pmod{n}, \quad n \geq 1,$$

for every $f \in \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{Z})$.

The equivalence of the conditions (1) and (2) was proved in [8]. On the other hand, it was observed in [1] that in the definition of the Dold-Fermat sequence the Möbius function can be replaced by the Euler totient function φ .

In the last section, we define the unitary analog of the Newton sequences. In particular, we show that a unitary Newton sequence is periodic if and only if it is bounded. We also prove that a p -periodic unitary sequence with prime period has to be constant.

2. Newton Sequences

Lemma 8. *Let $a \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$ and $f \in \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{Z})$. The following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) $\mu * a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$,
- (2) $f * a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$.

Proof. We first show that (1) implies (2). We have

$$f * a = \epsilon * f * a = \mu * I_0 * f * a = (\mu * a) * S_f \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z}),$$

by Corollary 3. Assume that (2) holds. We have

$$(\mu * a) * S_f = f * a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z}).$$

Since S_f belongs to $\mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z})$, S_f^{-1} does and by Corollary 3, one has

$$\mu * a = S_f^{-1} * (f * a) \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z}).$$

□

Remark 9. Observe that in the proof of implication (1) \implies (2) we need only that $S_f \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$ and f does not have to be invertible. In particular, one can take f of the form $f = \mu * g$ for some $g \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$.

As a consequence, one has the following result.

Theorem 10. *Assume that $a \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$. The following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) $a \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$,
- (2) $\mu * a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$,
- (3) $f * a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$ for every $f \in \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{Z})$.

Proof. The equivalence of the conditions (1) and (2) was proved in [8]. □

Lemma 11. *Let $f \in \mathcal{M}(\mathbb{Z})$. Then*

$$F : \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z}) \ni b \longmapsto f^{-1} * b \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$$

is a bijective map.

Proof. If $b \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$ then $f * f^{-1} * b = b \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$, hence $f^{-1} * b \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$ by Theorem 10, so F is well-defined. Since F is obviously injective, it is sufficient to show its surjectivity. If $a \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$ then $f * a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$, hence $f * a = b$ for some $b \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$, so $a = f^{-1} * b$. □

Corollary 12. *The following maps are bijective:*

- (a) $\mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z}) \ni b \mapsto \mu^{-1} * b = S_b \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$,
- (b) $\mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z}) \ni b \mapsto \varphi^{-1} * b = S_{\mu \cdot I_1} * b \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$.

Example 13 (Newton sequences). The following well-known sequences can be interpreted as Newton sequences:

- (1) $\sigma_1(n) = S_{I_1}(n) = \sum_{d|n} d$,
- (2) $\sigma_k(n) = S_{I_k}(n) = \sum_{d|n} d^k$,
- (3) $S_{\mu \cdot I_1} * (n!) = \sum_{d|n} d\mu(d)(n/d)!$,
- (4) $S_{\mu \cdot I_1} * I_k(n) = \sum_{d|n} d\mu(d)(n/d)^k = \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) \frac{n^k}{d^{k-1}}$.

Lemma 14. *If $a \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$ and $b \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$, then $a * b \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$.*

Proof. Since $b, \mu * a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$, we have

$$\mu * (a * b) = b * (\mu * a) \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z}),$$

so $a * b \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$. □

Example 15 (Newton sequences). The following sequences are Newton sequences:

- (1) $a * I_k(n) = \sum_{d|n} d^k a(n/d)$,
- (2) $b(n) = \sum_{d|n} a(n/d) d!$.

Corollary 16. *If $a, b \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$, then $\mu * a * b \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$.*

Corollary 17. *The map*

$$\mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z}) \times \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z}) \ni (b, a) \mapsto b * a \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$$

is an action of the group $\mathcal{A}_0^(\mathbb{Z})$ on the set $\mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$.*

We put

$$\mathcal{A}_{N_*}(\mathbb{Z}) = \{a \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z}) : a(1) \neq 0\}, \quad \mathcal{A}_{N_1}(\mathbb{Z}) = \{a \in \mathcal{A}_{N_*}(\mathbb{Z}) : a(1) = \pm 1\},$$

so $\mathcal{A}_{N_*}(\mathbb{Z})$ is the set of all invertible Newton sequences and for every $a \in \mathcal{A}_{N_1}(\mathbb{Z})$ the inverse of a belongs to $\mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$.

Example 18. We have $I_0 \in \mathcal{A}_{N_1}(\mathbb{Z})$, but $I_0^{-1} = \mu \notin \mathcal{A}_{N_1}(\mathbb{Z})$.

Lemma 19. *The map*

$$\mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z}) \times \mathcal{A}_{N_*}(\mathbb{Z}) \ni (b, a) \mapsto b * a \in \mathcal{A}_{N_*}(\mathbb{Z})$$

is a free but not transitive action of the group $\mathcal{A}_0^(\mathbb{Z})$ on the set $\mathcal{A}_{N_*}(\mathbb{Z})$.*

Proof. Since $b * a(1) = b(1)a(1) = \pm a(1) \neq 0$, $b * a \in \mathcal{A}_{N_*}(\mathbb{Z})$. We first show that the action is free. Let $b * a = a$. This implies $b = \epsilon$ because a is invertible. Next, we claim that the action is not transitive. It is obvious that $I_0, 2 \cdot I_0 \in \mathcal{A}_{N_*}(\mathbb{Z})$. Suppose that $b * I_0 = 2 \cdot I_0$ for some $b \in \mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z})$. Then $b = 2 \cdot \epsilon$ and $b(1) = 2 \neq \pm 1$. This creates a contradiction because $b \in \mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z})$. \square

Lemma 20. *The map*

$$\mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z}) \times \mathcal{A}_{N_1}(\mathbb{Z}) \ni (b, a) \mapsto b * a \in \mathcal{A}_{N_1}(\mathbb{Z})$$

is a free and transitive action of the group $\mathcal{A}_0^(\mathbb{Z})$ on $\mathcal{A}_{N_1}(\mathbb{Z})$.*

Proof. Since $b * a(1) = b(1)a(1) = \pm 1$, $b * a \in \mathcal{A}_{N_1}(\mathbb{Z})$. The action is free by Lemma 19. We show the transitivity of the action. For this, we consider two different elements a_1 and a_2 of $\mathcal{A}_{N_1}(\mathbb{Z})$. Let $b = a_1^{-1} * a_2$. We have $b * a_1 = a_2$ and $b(1) = \pm 1$, so it is sufficient to show that $b \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$. Since $\mu * a_1, \mu * a_2 \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$, we have

$$b = a_1^{-1} * I_0 * \mu * a_2 = (\mu * a_1)^{-1} * (\mu * a_2) \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z}).$$

\square

Corollary 21. *If $a_1, a_2 \in \mathcal{A}_{N_1}(\mathbb{Z})$, then $a_1^{-1} * a_2 \in \mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z})$.*

Example 22. For $\sigma_1 \in \mathcal{A}_{N_1}(\mathbb{Z})$, we have $\sigma_1^{-1} = (\mu \cdot I_1) * \mu$, hence $(\mu \cdot I_1) * \mu * a \in \mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z})$ for all $a \in \mathcal{A}_{N_1}(\mathbb{Z})$.

Proposition 23. $\mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z}) \cap \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z}) = \{0^\infty\}$.

Proof. We use the induction with respect to n . Assume that $n = 1$. Since $a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z}) \cap \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$, for prime p we have $a(p) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ and $a(p) \equiv a(1) \pmod{p}$. It follows that $a(1) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ for every prime p , i.e., $a(1) = 0$. Let $n \geq 2$ and assume that $a(1) = \dots = a(n-1) = 0$. We show that $a(n) = 0$. Let $p > n$ be a prime number. We have

$$\sum_{d|pn} \mu(d)a\left(\frac{pn}{d}\right) = \sum_{d|n} \mu(d)a\left(\frac{pn}{d}\right) + \sum_{d|n} \mu(pd)a\left(\frac{n}{d}\right) \equiv 0 \pmod{pn},$$

and consequently,

$$\sum_{d|n} \mu(d)a\left(\frac{pn}{d}\right) - a(n) \equiv 0 \pmod{pn}.$$

On the other hand, $a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$ implies that $a\left(\frac{pn}{d}\right) \equiv 0 \pmod{\frac{pn}{d}}$ for all $d|n$, hence $a\left(\frac{pn}{d}\right) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$. It follows that $a(n) \equiv 0 \pmod{p}$ for every prime $p > n$, and $a(n) = 0$. \square

3. Unitary Newton Sequences

We recall that d is a *unitary divisor* of the positive integer n if $d|n$ and $(d, n/d) = 1$. It will be denoted by $d||n$. Obviously, $1||n$ and $n||n$. For $f, g \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$ we define their *unitary convolution* $f \circ g$ by the formula

$$f \circ g(n) = \sum_{d||n} f(d)g(n/d), \quad n \geq 1.$$

Notice that $f \circ g(n) = f * g(n)$ for all square-free $n \geq 1$. We summarize some well-known facts concerning unitary convolution.

- The Dirichlet and the unitary convolution, have the same identity element ϵ .
- If $f \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$ satisfies $f(1) = \pm 1$, then f has the unitary inverse $\bar{f}^{-1} \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$.
- The *unitary sum function* \bar{S}_f is defined as

$$\bar{S}_f(n) = f \circ I_0(n) = \sum_{d||n} f(d), \quad n \geq 1.$$

- The *unitary Möbius function* $\bar{\mu}$ is defined as the unitary inverse of I_0 , i.e., $\bar{\mu} * I_0 = \epsilon$. Since $\bar{\mu}$ is multiplicative, it is determined by its values at the powers of primes. We have

$$0 = \sum_{d||p^k} \bar{\mu}(d) = \bar{\mu}(p^k) + \bar{\mu}(1),$$

hence $\bar{\mu}(p^k) = -1$ and $\bar{\mu}(n) = (-1)^{\omega(n)}$, where $\omega(n)$ is the number of distinct prime factors of n .

Definition 24 (Unitary Newton sequence). Let $a \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$. We say that a is a *unitary Newton sequence*, if $\bar{\mu} \circ a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$, i.e.,

$$\sum_{d||n} (-1)^{\omega(d)} a(n/d) \equiv 0 \pmod{n}, \quad n \geq 1.$$

By $\mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$ we denote the set of all unitary Newton sequences.

Corollary 25. For $a \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$ the following conditions are equivalent:

- (1) $a \in \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$,
- (2) $a = \bar{S}_b = b \circ I_0$ for some $b \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$.

Proof. Obviously, $\bar{\mu} \circ a = b$ for some $b \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$ is equivalent to $a = b \circ I_0 = \bar{S}_b$ for some $b \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$. □

Example 26. The sum of unitary divisors function $\bar{\sigma}_1$ given by

$$\bar{\sigma}_1(n) = \sum_{d||n} d = \bar{S}_{I_1}(n).$$

It follows that $\bar{\sigma}_1 \in \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$, but $\bar{\sigma}_1 \notin \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$. Indeed, for prime p we have

$$\bar{\sigma}_1(p^2) = 1 + p^2, \quad \bar{\sigma}_1(p) = 1 + p,$$

hence

$$\sum_{d|p^2} \mu(d) \bar{\sigma}_1(p^2/d) = \bar{\sigma}_1(p^2) - \bar{\sigma}_1(p) = p^2 - p \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p^2}.$$

Example 27. The sum of k -th powers of the unitary divisors of n , i.e.,

$$\bar{\sigma}_k(n) = \sum_{d||n} d^k = \bar{S}_{I_k}(n), \quad k \geq 1,$$

is a unitary Newton sequence.

Corollary 28. For $a \in \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$ the following conditions hold:

- (1) $a(p^k) \equiv a(1) \pmod{p^k}$ for all prime p and $k \geq 1$,
- (2) if a is bounded and p is prime, then $a(p^k) = a(1)$ for almost all $k \geq 1$,
- (3) if n is square-free, then

$$\bar{\mu} \circ a(n) = \sum_{d||n} (-1)^{\omega(d)} a(n/d) = \sum_{d|n} \mu(d) a(n/d) \equiv 0 \pmod{n},$$

- (4) if $a \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z}) \cap \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$, then $a(p^{k-1}) \equiv a(1) \pmod{p^k}$ for prime p and $k \geq 1$.

Proposition 29. If $a \in \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$ is p -periodic with a prime p , then a is constant.

Proof. Since $\bar{\mu} \circ a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$, $a(p) \equiv a(1) \pmod{p}$. We first show that $a(1) = \dots = a(p-1)$. Let $l \in \{2, \dots, p-1\}$. We consider the arithmetic progression $p_k = l + kp$. Then, by the Dirichlet theorem, p_k is a prime number for infinitely many $k \geq 1$. If p_k is prime, then $a(1) \equiv a(p_k) = a(l) \pmod{p_k}$. Consequently, $a(1) \equiv a(l) \pmod{p_k}$ for infinitely many primes p_k . This shows that $a(1) = a(l)$. It remains to prove that $a(1) = a(p)$. We have that $a(p^k) = a(p)$ because a is p -periodic. It follows by Corollary 28 that $a(p) \equiv a(1) \pmod{p^k}$ for all $k \geq 1$. This means that $a(p) = a(1)$. □

Example 30. Let $k, l \in \mathbb{Z}$ be such that $k \equiv l \pmod{p}$ for prime p . Let a be a p -periodic sequence such that $a(1) = \dots = a(p-1) = l$ and $a(p) = k$. If $l \neq k$, then $a \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$ and $a \notin \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$.

Example 31. Let $a(n) = 2^n$. Then $a \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$ and $a \notin \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$. More generally, let $a(n) = m^n$ for some positive integer $m \geq 1$. One can check that, $a \in \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$ if and only if $m = 1$.

Let $\tau(n) = \sum_{d|n} 1$ be the number of divisors of $n \geq 1$ and $\tau^\circ(n) = \sum_{d||n} 1$ be the number of unitary divisors of n . Since one of two complementary divisors of n is always not greater than \sqrt{n} , one has

$$\tau^\circ(n) \leq \tau(n) \leq 2\sqrt{n}.$$

It follows that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\tau(n)}{n} = 0.$$

Lemma 32. Let $a \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$ ($a \in \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$) be a bounded sequence and let $\|a\|_\infty = \max\{|a_i| : i \geq 1\}$. If $n > 4\|a\|_\infty^2$, then

$$(\mu * a)(n) = 0 \quad ((\bar{\mu} \circ a)(n) = 0).$$

Proof. We have

$$|(\mu * a)(n)| \leq \sum_{d|n} |a(n/d)| \leq \|a\|_\infty \sum_{d|n} 1 \leq 2\|a\|_\infty \sqrt{n},$$

hence $|(\mu * a)(n)| < n$ for $n > 4\|a\|_\infty^2$. Since $(\mu * a)(n) \equiv 0 \pmod{n}$, $(\mu * a)(n) = 0$ for $n > 4\|a\|_\infty^2$. The proof in the unitary case is exactly the same because

$$\tau^\circ(n) \leq \tau(n) \leq 2\sqrt{n}.$$

□

Lemma 33. Let $a \in \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$ be p^k -periodic for some prime p and $k \geq 1$. Then $a(p^k) = a(1)$.

Proof. We have $a(p^k) = a(p^l p^k) = a(p^{l+k}) = a(1)$ for l sufficiently large. □

Definition 34. Let $k \geq 1$. We define $\bar{b}_k \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$ by

$$\bar{b}_k(n) = \begin{cases} k, & \text{if } n = k \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

It follows that $\bar{S}_{\bar{b}_k} \in \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$ and

$$\bar{S}_{\bar{b}_k}(n) = \sum_{d||n} \bar{b}_k(d) = \begin{cases} k, & \text{if } k||n \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

Let us observe that $\bar{S}_{\bar{b}_k}$ is k^2 -periodic. Indeed, it is easy to check that $k||n$ if and only if $k|(n + k^2)$. This shows that $\bar{S}_{\bar{b}_k}(n) = \bar{S}_{\bar{b}_k}(n + k^2)$.

Proposition 35. *Let $a \in \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$. The following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) a is bounded,
- (2) there exist $l \geq 1$ and integers $x_k \in \mathbb{Z}$ for $1 \leq k \leq l$ such that

$$a = \sum_{k=1}^l x_k \bar{S}_{\bar{b}_k},$$

- (3) a is periodic.

Proof. Obviously, (2) implies (3) and (3) implies (1). We show that (1) implies (2). Assume that a is bounded and $|a(n)| \leq M$ for $n \geq 1$. Since $a = \bar{S}_b$, with $b \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$, $a = \bar{S}_{I \cdot \bar{b}}$ for some $\bar{b} \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$. We have $I \cdot \bar{b} = \bar{\mu} * a$, so

$$|\bar{b}(n)| = \frac{1}{n} \left| \sum_{d|n} \bar{\mu}(d) a(n/d) \right| \leq \frac{M}{n} \sum_{d|n} 1 \leq M \frac{\tau(n)}{n}.$$

Since $\frac{\tau(n)}{n} \rightarrow 0$, $\bar{b}(n) \rightarrow 0$. On the other hand, \bar{b} is a sequence of integers, so there exists $l \geq 1$ such that $\bar{b}(n) = 0$ for $n > l$. It follows that

$$b = (b(1), \dots, b(l), 0, \dots) = \sum_{k=1}^l \frac{b(k)}{k} \bar{b}_k,$$

and consequently,

$$a = \bar{S}_b = \sum_{k=1}^l x_k \bar{S}_{\bar{b}_k}, \quad x_k = \frac{b(k)}{k}.$$

□

Remark 36. For $k \geq 1$ we consider the sequence $b_k \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$ given as

$$b_k(n) = \begin{cases} k, & \text{if } n = k \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

It follows that $S_{b_k} \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$ and

$$S_{b_k}(n) = \sum_{d|n} b_k(d) = \begin{cases} k, & \text{if } k|n \\ 0, & \text{otherwise.} \end{cases}$$

The proof of Proposition 35 shows the well-known fact that a Newton sequence $a \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$ is bounded if and only if there are $l \geq 1$ and integers x_1, \dots, x_l such that

$$a = \sum_{k=1}^l x_k S_{b_k}.$$

Lemma 37. *If $a, f \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$ are such that $\bar{\mu} \circ a, \bar{S}_f \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$, then $f \circ a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$. In particular, $a \in \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$ implies $f \circ a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$.*

Proof. Corollary 3 implies that

$$f \circ a = \epsilon \circ f \circ a = \bar{\mu} \circ I_0 \circ f \circ a = (\bar{\mu} \circ a) \circ \bar{S}_f \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z}).$$

□

Lemma 38. *If $a, f \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$ are such that $f \circ a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$, $\bar{S}_f \in \mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z})$, then $\bar{\mu} \circ a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$. In particular, $f \circ a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$ implies that $a \in \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$ provided that $\bar{S}_f \in \mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z})$.*

Proof. We have

$$(\bar{\mu} \circ a) \circ \bar{S}_f = f \circ a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z}).$$

Since $\bar{S}_f \in \mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z})$, $\bar{S}_f^{-1} \in \mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z})$. Consequently, Corollary 3 shows that

$$\bar{\mu} \circ a = \bar{S}_f^{-1} \circ (f \circ a) \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z}).$$

□

Corollary 39. *Assume that $a \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$ and $\bar{S}_f \in \mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z})$. The following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) $a \in \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$,
- (2) $f \circ a \in \mathcal{A}_0(\mathbb{Z})$.

Proof. It follows by Lemma 37 and Lemma 38. □

Example 40. The *unitary Euler totient function* is defined by $\bar{\phi} := \bar{\mu} \circ I_1$, i.e.,

$$\bar{\phi}(n) = \sum_{d|n} \bar{\mu}(d) \frac{n}{d}.$$

Obviously,

$$\bar{S}_{\bar{\phi}} = \bar{\phi} \circ I_0 = \bar{\mu} \circ I_1 \circ I_0 = I_1 \in \mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z}).$$

Similarly, $\bar{S}_{\bar{\phi}_k} \in \mathcal{A}_0^*(\mathbb{Z})$ for $\bar{\phi}_k := \bar{\mu} \circ I_k$.

It was proved in [7] that $a \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z})$ if and only if

$$a(n) \equiv a(n/p) \pmod{p^k},$$

for any $n \in \mathbb{N}$ and for any prime p with $p^k | n$ (i.e., $p^k | n$ and $n \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p^{k+1}}$).

Proposition 41. *Let $a \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$. The following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) $a \in \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$,
- (2) $a(n) \equiv a(n/p^k) \pmod{p^k}$ for any $n \geq 1$ and any prime p with $p^k \parallel n$.

Proof. First, we show that (1) implies (2). We use the induction with respect to $\omega(n)$, i.e., the number of prime factors of n . If $\omega(n) = 1$, then $n = p^k$ and the result follows by Corollary 28. Assume that formula holds for $\omega(n) = r$. We prove it for $\omega(n) = r + 1$. Let $n = p_1^{k_1} p_2^{k_2} \dots p_{r+1}^{k_{r+1}}$ with different primes p_i and $k_i \geq 1$. By symmetry, it is sufficient to show that $a(n) \equiv a(n/p_1^{k_1}) \pmod{p_1^{k_1}}$. We consider the set

$$S = \{d : d \parallel n, d \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p_1^{k_1}}\}.$$

We have

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mu} \circ a(n) &= \sum_{d \parallel n} (-1)^{\omega(d)} a(n/d) \\ &= \sum_{d \in S} (-1)^{\omega(d)} a(n/d) + (-1)^{\omega(p_1^{k_1} d)} a(n/p_1^{k_1} d) \\ &= a(n) - a(n/p_1^{k_1}) + \sum_{\substack{d \in S \\ d \neq 1, d \neq p_1^{k_1}}} (-1)^{\omega(d)} (a(n/d) - a(n/p_1^{k_1} d)). \end{aligned}$$

Obviously, $\bar{\mu} \circ a(n) \equiv 0 \pmod{p_1^{k_1}}$ and by the inductive step

$$\sum_{\substack{d \in S \\ d \neq 1, d \neq p_1^{k_1}}} (-1)^{\omega(d)} (a(n/d) - a(n/p_1^{k_1} d)) \equiv 0 \pmod{p_1^{k_1}}.$$

It follows that $a(n) - a(n/p_1^{k_1}) \equiv 0 \pmod{p_1^{k_1}}$.

Next, we show that (2) implies (1). We have to show that $\bar{\mu} \circ a(n) \equiv 0 \pmod{n}$. We proceed by induction on $\omega(n)$. If $\omega(n) = 1$, then $n = p^k$ and the result follows by (2). Assume that formula holds for $\omega(n) = r$. We will prove it for $\omega(n) = r + 1$. Let $n = p_1^{k_1} p_2^{k_2} \dots p_{r+1}^{k_{r+1}}$ with different primes p_i and $k_i \geq 1$. We set

$$S_i = \{d : d \parallel n, d \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p_i^{k_i}}\}.$$

We have

$$\bar{\mu} \circ a(n) = a(n) - a(n/p_i^{k_i}) + \sum_{\substack{d \in S_i \\ d \neq 1, d \neq p_i^{k_i}}} (-1)^{\omega(d)} (a(n/d) - a(n/p_i^{k_i} d)).$$

By the inductive step

$$\sum_{\substack{d \in S_i \\ d \neq 1, d \neq p_i^{k_i}}} (-1)^{\omega(d)} (a(n/d) - a(n/p_i^{k_i} d)) \equiv 0 \pmod{p_i^{k_i}},$$

and $a(n) - a(n/p_i^{k_i}) \equiv 0 \pmod{p_i^{k_i}}$ by (2). We conclude that $\bar{\mu} \circ a(n) \equiv 0 \pmod{p_i^{k_i}}$ for all $i = 1, \dots, r + 1$, and the result follows. \square

Corollary 42. *Let $a \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$. The following conditions are equivalent:*

- (1) $a \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z}) \cap \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$,
- (2) $a(n) \equiv a(n/p) \equiv a(n/p^k) \pmod{p^k}$ for any $n \geq 1$ and all prime p with $p^k \parallel n$.

In particular, if $a \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z}) \cap \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$, then

$$a(p^k) \equiv a(1) \pmod{p^{k+1}},$$

for prime p and $k \geq 1$.

Example 43. If $a \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$ is constant, then $a \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z}) \cap \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$.

Example 44. The sequence

$$a_2(n) = \begin{cases} 2^{k+1}, & \text{if } 2^k \parallel n \text{ for some } k \geq 1 \\ 0, & \text{if } n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}, \end{cases}$$

belongs to $\mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z}) \cap \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$. Indeed, we have

- (i) $a_2(n) = a_2(n/p) = a_2(n/p^s) = 0$ if n is odd and $p^s \parallel n$,
- (ii) $a_2(n) = a_2(n/p) = a_2(n/p^s) = 2^{k+1}$ if $n = 2^k m$ ($k \geq 1$) with m odd and $p^s \parallel m$,
- (iii) for m odd and $k \geq 1$ we have $a_2(2^k m) = 2^{k+1}$, $a_2(2^k m/2^k) = a_2(m) = 0$ and

$$a_2(2^k m/2) = a_2(2^{k-1} m) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } k = 1 \\ 2^k, & \text{if } k > 1. \end{cases}$$

More generally, let p be a fixed prime. Then $a_p \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z}) \cap \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$, where

$$a_p(n) = \begin{cases} p^{k+1}, & \text{if } p^k \parallel n \text{ for some } k \geq 1 \\ 0, & \text{if } n \not\equiv 0 \pmod{p}. \end{cases}$$

Example 45. We show that the sequence a_2 defined in Example 44 is not a sequence of traces. Let $c \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$ be a sequence of integers generating a_2 , i.e.,

$$a_2(n) = c(1)a_2(n - 1) + \dots + c(n - 1)a_2(1) + nc(n), \quad n \geq 1.$$

It is sufficient to show that c is infinite, i.e., there is no $l \geq 1$ such that $c(n) = 0$ for $n > l$. We first claim that $c(m) = 0$ for all odd $m \geq 1$. Obviously, we have

$0 = a_2(1) = c(1)$. Assume that $a(s) = 0$ for all odd s less than some odd $m > 1$. Then

$$0 = a_2(m) = c(1)a_2(m-1) + \dots + c(m-1)a_2(1) + mc(m).$$

Since m is odd, i and $m-i$ have different parity for all $i = 1, \dots, m-1$. By the inductive step $c(i)a_2(m-i) = 0$. Consequently, $c(m) = 0$. Next, suppose that c is finite, i.e.,

$$c = (0, c(2), 0, c(4), \dots, 0, c(2s), 0, 0, \dots)$$

for some $s \geq 1$. Then $2s = 2^t m$ for some $t \geq 1$ and odd m . Let $r \geq 1$ be such that $|c(2i)| \leq 2^r$ for $i = 1, \dots, s$. For all $k > 2s$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} 2^{k+1} &= a_2(2^k) = c(2)a_2(2^k-2) + \dots + c(2s)a_2(2^k-2s) \\ &= c(2)a_2(2(2^{k-1}-1)) + \dots + c(2s)a_2(2^t(2^{k-t}-m)) \\ &= c(2)2^2 + \dots + c(2s)2^{t+1}. \end{aligned}$$

Since

$$\begin{aligned} |a_2(2^k)| &= |c(2)a_2(2^k-2) + \dots + c(2s)a_2(2^k-2s)| \\ &\leq 2^r(2^2 + \dots + 2^{t+1}) \leq s2^{r+t+1}, \end{aligned}$$

we get a contradiction by taking k sufficiently large.

Problem 46. The following natural questions are worth of consideration:

- describe $\mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z}) \cap \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$,
- characterize the integer matrices $A \in M_I(\mathbb{Z})$ such that $\text{tr}[A] \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z}) \cap \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$ (obviously, $\text{tr}[I] \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z}) \cap \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$),
- characterize the generating sequences $c \in \mathcal{A}(\mathbb{Z})$ for $a \in \mathcal{A}_N(\mathbb{Z}) \cap \mathcal{A}_{UN}(\mathbb{Z})$.

References

[1] S. András, A combinatorial generalizations of Wilson’s theorem, *Australas. J. Combin.* **49** (2011), 265-272.
 [2] T. M. Apostol, *Introduction to Analytic Number Theory*, Springer-Verlag 1976.
 [3] J. Arias de Reyna, Dynamical zeta functions and Krumer congruences, *Acta Arith.* **119** (2005), 39-52.
 [4] V. I. Arnold, On the matricial version of Fermat-Euler congruences, *Jpn. J. Math.* **3** (2006), 1-24.
 [5] I. K. Babenko, S. A. Bogaty, The behavior of the index of periodic points under iterations of a mapping, *Math. USSR Izv.* **38** (1992), 1-26.

- [6] A. Dold, Fixed point indices of iterated maps, *Invent. Math.* **74** (1983), 419-435.
- [7] B.-S. Du, S.-S. Huang, M.-C. Li, Generalized Fermat, Double Fermat and Newton Sequences, *J. Number Theory* **98** (2003), 172-183.
- [8] B.-S. Du, S.-S. Huang, M.-C. Li, Newton, Fermat, and exactly realizable sequences, *J. Integer Seq.*, **8** (2005), Article 05.1.2.
- [9] F. S. Gillespie, A generalization of Fermat's little theorem, *Fibonacci Quart.* **27** (1989), 109-115.
- [10] G. T. Minton, Linear recurrence sequences satisfying congruence conditions, *Proc. Amer. Math. Soc.* **142** (2014), no. 7, 2337-2352.
- [11] N. Neumärker, Realizability of integer sequences as differences of fixed point count sequences, *J. Integer Seq.* **12** (2009), Article 09.4.5, 8.
- [12] H. Steinlein, Fermat's Little Theorem and Gauss congruence: matrix versions and cyclic permutations, *Amer. Math. Monthly*, **124** (2017), 548-553.
- [13] Z.-H. Sun, Linear recursive sequences and powers of matrices, *Fibonacci Quart.* **39** (2001), 339-351.
- [14] K. Wójcik, Binomial transform and Dold sequences, *J. Integer Seq.*, **18** (2015), Article 15.1.1.
- [15] A. V. Zaruela, On congruences for the traces of powers of some matrices, *Proc. Steklov Inst. Math.*, **263** (2008), 78-98.